

MEDIA CULTURE AND INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES.

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Abstract: This article describes the essence of the use of innovative pedagogical technologies and their role and importance in improving the quality of education. Also, this article discusses the effectiveness of using innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process and offers suggestions for a new approach to the educational process in higher education institutions.

Key words: Technologies, media, pedagogical, innovation, education

In cultural studies, media culture refers to the current Western capitalist society that emerged and developed from the 20th century, under the influence of mass media. The term alludes to the overall impact and intellectual guidance exerted by the media (primarily TV, but also the press, radio and cinema), not only on public opinion but also on tastes and values. The alternative term mass culture conveys the idea that such culture emerges spontaneously from the masses themselves, like popular art did before the 20th century. The expression media culture, on the other hand, conveys the idea that such culture is the product of the mass media. Another alternative term for media culture is "image culture.

Media culture, with its declinations of advertising and public relations, is often considered as a system centered on the manipulation of the mass of society. Corporate media "are used primarily to represent and reproduce dominant ideologies." Prominent in the development of this perspective has been the work of Theodor Adorno since the 1940s. Media culture is associated with consumerism, and in this sense called alternatively "consumer culture." Pedagogical technology is a system of modern organization of the educational process which ensures the necessary quality of education and accelerated scientific and technical development aimed at the task of improving educational forms that meet the requirements technical and human factors of teaching processes, their joint actions qis a consistent method of creating, implementing. Innovative in the educational process the use of pedagogical technologies is the demand of the times. Pedagogical technology-technical resources, people and their interaction taking into account the task of optimizing educational forms and creation, application and determination of all processes of knowledge

acquisition systematic method (UNESCO). In the process of education, he used new innovative techniques and technologies lessons, from laboratory rooms equipped with the latest techniques conducting training using it, in a specialty, for example, chemistry from the world experience, providing information about the latest innovations in the field citing examples is an incentive to educate students in the spirit of innovation will be.

Technologies used in the process of innovative education are innovative education technologies or educational innovations. Innovative pedagogical technologies will be in demand in the labor market in the future education for the preparation of available modern specialists is very important in the process. The pedagogue himself has modern ICT for training modern personnel using tools, the latest scientific achievements, knowledge itself to be aware of the news of the field and the latest pedagogy technology-based lessons are required. Our country in the concept of development of higher education until 2030 the goal is to include higher educational institutions in the ranks of international 1000 educational institutions done But the international experience of innovative pedagogical technologies learning and their application is being carried out relatively slowly.

The profession in which the greatest demand is directed now and in the future is IT are experts. These directions should be opened more in higher education institutions and The pedagogues are well-educated and well-educated in order to train mature personnel in this field have pedagogical skills and teach based on innovative technologies. Here it is with modern techniques and technologists to achieve success in such fields a higher education institution where classes are held on the basis of provided and innovative pedagogical technologies we think that educational institutions are definitely among the best institutions.

The teacher is innovative in working on the basis of innovative pedagogical technologies there should be an understanding of the activity. Innovative activity is scientific in nature research, creating developments, conducting experimental work, science and technology from creating a new improved product based on the use of achievements consists of The innovative activity of a teacher is determined by: - readiness to use the innovation; - acceptance of pedagogical innovations; - level of innovation; - development of communication skills; - creativity.

Innovative activity is in accordance with the traditional standards of new social requirements absence or denial of existing ideas by newly forming ideas

activities aimed at solving complex problems arising as a result. Innovative activity requires the spiritual, mental and physical strength of a pedagogue acquisition of knowledge, skills, and practical activities based on goal orientation filling with theoretical knowledge, knowledge, design, communicative speech and requires the development of organizational skills.

At the 1st stage, a ready-made methodological description (existing innovation, for example, foreign used in the experience, but new for us) will be used.

In the 2nd stage, the pedagogue introduces his new ideas and methods into the existing system.

It is at the 3rd stage of deciding on the innovative approach of pedagogues. He is working on the idea and innovative method created in the second stage systematizes the content, forms and methods of implementation in the institution.

At the 4th stage, the pedagogue has his own concept (ideas) of teaching and training total) or creates methodology.

Summary

In short, innovative in education pedagogical if the use of technologies increases the quality of education, innovative technologies is the driving force of educational development. The future of every society is its own To what extent is the education system, which is an integral part and a vital necessity determined by its development. Today, through independent development reforming and improving the continuous education system of our growing country, raising it to a new level of quality, introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies, and increasing the effectiveness of education was expected at the level of state policy.

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